

**Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part XIV.
Coagulation of Colloid Arsenious Sulphide by
Mercuric Chloride. Inadmissibility of Viscosity and Transparency as General Criteria
of Coagulation.**

BY SHRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI AND SADASHIV S. KULKARNI.

Arising out of work which has been in progress for some time in these laboratories, on the coagulative powers of aqueous solutions of mercury chloride relative to those of other electrolytes to be published shortly, was the question of the variation of the viscosity and of the light transparency of a sol subjected to coagulation by mercury chloride. Reference to the literature showed that the rôle of this electrolyte as a coagulant has not received the adequate attention, which a consideration of some of its physico-chemical properties suggests. The present work was therefore undertaken with a view to supply the deficiency of our knowledge in this line.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sol was prepared by adding in small quantities from a paste of arsenious acid to twice distilled water which was kept boiling. After filtering and allowing it to cool, a current of hydrogen sulphide, washed previously by leading through water, was passed very slowly and with continuous shaking. The excess of the gas was then driven off by a current of hydrogen. The colloid content was estimated by a method described previously (Joshi and Nanjappa, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 135). It was 18.1 g. of arsenious sulphide per litre. Equal volumes of the colloid and of the coagulator solution were allowed to attain the temperature of the thermostat, *viz.*, $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, and mixed in the Scarpa tube of the viscometer. Three concentrations for the colloid in the coagulation mixture were employed in experiments referred to in Figs. 1-4, *viz.*, $C/1=9.03$, $C/2=4.51$ and $C/8=1.13$ g. arsenious sulphide per litre. The viscosity was measured by the Scarpa's method with modifications as described previously (Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 599). The suction applied to the liquid to

be examined was kept constant at 31.5 ± 0.01 cm. of water in all the experiments. This pressure was such as gave approximately equal times for the rise and the fall of the liquid through the capillary in the Scarpa tube, as required by the theory of the instrument for maximum accuracy (*loc. cit.*). It is known that particularly in the case of colloids, validity of the data for viscosity depends upon whether the measurements were made under conditions of *viscous flow*. This was ascertained in the present work by the observation that the time for rise for the colloid used under a large number of pressures in the neighbourhood of the above value was clearly a *linear* function of the applied pressure. The constant k involved in the equation,

$$\eta = k \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2},$$

(where t_1 , t_2 and η are the the times for the rise, the fall of the liquid and its viscosity respectively) was found to be 0.007033, when η for

water was taken to be 0.7958 C.P. (*cf.* Bingham, "Fluidity and Plasticity," 1922, p. 339). These measurements were continued till the appearance of the coagulum as discrete particles on the walls of the viscometer became just perceptible. In the majority of cases this stage was observable easily and fairly unambiguously, and has been indicated by an arrow on the viscosity-time curve, when the viscosity measurements were continued beyond this stage. The degree of reproducibility of these results using pure liquids was easily 1-2 in 1000.

FIG. 1.

Continued at x.

Variations less than at least ten times this quantity have not been considered in the data recorded in this paper. The results for the change of viscosity, when the colloid concentration was varied up to eight-fold and that of mercury chloride varied in the range $N/500$ to $N/2000$, are shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2. It might be added that use of concentrations higher than $N/500$ produced coagulations which were too quick for viscosity and other measurements. Viscosity measurements were also made during coagulations due to mercury chloride mixed with *small* amounts of other electrolytes; of these only one typical result, when $N/150$ -KCl was added, is shown graphically by curve 17 in Fig. 2. Curves shown in Fig. 3 show just a few typical cases of a much greater number of curves obtained showing the change of viscosity when the coagulants were solutions of potassium and cadmium chloride under the same conditions, for comparison with coagulations by mercuric chloride.

In view of the unexpected results obtained in respect of viscosity, it was thought desirable to examine the variation of another property, transparency which has been so widely employed in measurements of coagulation. This has been determined by two different methods. The first series of experiments, some of which are represented by the time-transparency curves in Fig. 4, were carried out using a thermopile, whose readings on light let through in the coagulating sol were taken by means of a sensitive Broca galvanometer. Complete details as regards the method of observation, the precautions taken are reported in an earlier paper (Part XIII) in this series. In the next series of experiments, the opacity of the coagulating sol was determined directly by means of a Duboscq colorimeter. The apparatus consisted essentially of two similar tubes illuminated from the bottom. Each of these carried a fairly well fitting empty tube moving co-axially. The underfaces of the inside tubes showed the same position on the vertical scale fixed on the instrument, when the outer tubes were symmetrically illuminated by a given beam of light and when the same liquid was present in both the outer tubes, the emergent light from both the tubes being matched for equality of intensity through an eye-piece. In actual measurements, one of the tubes was filled with a convenient volume of the colloid diluted with an equal volume of pure water. The other limb contained the same amount of the colloid mixed with an equal volume of any of the coagulating solutions. By shifting the tube in the latter therefore, a measure of the opacity of the coagulating sol was obtained relative to that of the colloid diluted with water

in the difference in the positions of the two columns, when matching. These results with mercuric and potassium chlorides are shown by curves in Fig. 5.

DISCUSSION.

It has been almost a tacit assumption with colloid chemists that coagulation produces necessarily an increase of viscosity (and of opacity, *vide infra*), and many workers have supposed that the last quantity is a measure of the corresponding degree of coagulation. The viscosity-time curves in Figs. 1 and 2 show that coagulations with mercuric chloride negate this generalisation, in failing to show an over-all rise of viscosity, in by far the majority of cases. Two features are, however, noticeable in almost all the curves :

(i) There is an initial fall of viscosity which has been observed previously in numerous coagulations with different sols and coagulants (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 323; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, p. 599; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 133; Joshi and Iyengar, *ibid.*, pp. 555, 574; Joshi and Panikkar, *ibid.*, p. 797; *cf.* also, *Proc. Acad. Sci., U. P.*, 1935, **5**, 41; *J. chim. phys.*, 1935, **32**, 455).

(ii) The progress of the viscosity change during coagulation is 'zonal,' that is, occurs through breaks, although a given coagulation-time curve does not show a sensible net rise of viscosity except in curves 7 and 10 in Fig. 1, where the rise sets in only after an extremely long time after the start of coagulation, *viz.*, 980 and 1400 minutes respectively.

It is interesting to compare the curves in Figs. 1 and 2 for mercury chloride with those in Fig. 3 due to cadmium and potassium chlorides. The difference is well marked. With higher concentrations of these electrolytes, the viscosity increases on the whole during coagulation, the increase being 'zonal' or discontinuous. With low concentrations there is no net increase of viscosity, but merely a number of breaks, which is precisely in agreement with earlier results (Joshi and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). *The abnormality in the case of mercury chloride is revealed by the fact, that even if a higher concentration of this coagulator is used, what is produced is flocculation which comes down as a precipitate in due time, but no rise of viscosity, so familiar in coagulation phenomena.* It is also interesting to consider the curve No. 17

in Fig. 2. When mixed with $N/962\text{-HgCl}_2$ only, it was observed that a curve only with an initial fall and a number of breaks, but without an over-all increase of viscosity could be observed even after very considerable time. Essentially the same result was obtained when $N/150\text{-KCl}$ was used as a coagulant (*cf.* curve 16, Fig. 3). When, however, the two electrolytes were mixed, the curve is wholly normal; it shows an appreciable over-all rise in viscosity during a comparatively shorter period; the flocculation also was observed comparatively early. It might be mentioned that detailed studies were made of the viscosity changes in two other colloids, *viz.*, colloid manganese dioxide and colloid antimony sulphide in the presence of mercuric chloride to see if these also showed an absence of viscosity rise. The results showed that these sols behaved normally, that is, they always showed a net rise in viscosity when the coagulant was reasonably concentrated. The conclusion is, therefore, suggested that the above results seem to be a peculiarity of the arsenious sulphide sol with mercury chloride as the coagulant. It might be also mentioned at this stage that the coagulum obtained in experiments with mercuric chloride, was examined outside the viscometer; it felt to be comparatively more *gritty*, and unlike the soft, almost filamented and gelatin-like mass observed usually. It is suggested as a tentative hypothesis that this absence of viscosity rise might be due appreciably to the above character of coagulum, and experiments are now in progress to obtain more information in regard to this possibility. Results have been obtained previously (Joshi and Nanjappa, Joshi and Iyengar, *loc. cit.*) to show that in a number of coagulations, the viscosity showed antinormal variation, *viz.*, a very marked and over-all diminution, the curve being *zonal*. These results together with the present findings suggest that it is not unlikely that the rise of viscosity might not depend entirely on such a single micellar property as the charge, the size, etc., but rather on some additional factors leading to a kind of meshwork-like or aggregate structure, which grows in the coagulating system from the very incipience of the change.

It is interesting to see (from the curves in Figs. 4 and 5) that the variations of transparency (Fig. 4) and of opacity (Fig. 5) during coagulations with mercuric chloride show a striking parallelism with the corresponding results of viscosity measurements, *viz.*, that both these quantities do not change. It must be emphasised that the measurements of these related quantities, *viz.*, transparency and opacity were made by completely independent methods. Their mutual agreement is, therefore, of importance. The rise in transparency shown by curves 20 and 23 in Fig. 4 was due to the fact that the precipitation of the coagulum, set in almost from the start of coagulation as shown by the arrow on the curve, with the result that

Curves 1-5 refer respectively to 0.67 g., 1.13 g., 2.25 g., 0.57 g. and 0.57 g. As_2S_3 per litre. Curves with $HgCl_2$ refer to 2.23 g. per litre.

the transparency of the system approached that of the continuous medium, *viz.*, water. As in the viscosity results, this finding is peculiar to the use of the above coagulant; this is shown by a few typical curves (No. 25, 26 and 27 in Fig. 4 and No. 5 in Fig. 5), when other coagulants like cadmium and potassium chlorides were employed, under the same conditions. Also as observed in the case of viscosity measurements, transparency (Fig. 4) and the inverse of opacity (Fig. 5) do not appreciably diminish if only a low concentration of the normal coagulant say potassium chloride is employed (*vide* curve 26, Fig. 4, curve 1, Fig. 5). As soon as, however, its concentration is raised, we get the familiar reduction of transparency (*cf.* curve 25, Fig. 4) and rise of opacity (curves 4, 5 in Fig. 5). The abnormality of mercury chloride is once more brought out by the fact that the transparency does not diminish (and the opacity does not rise) even though the concentration of this coagulant is increased. Under the latter condition it produces flocculation and the precipitate actually tends to settle down, that is, mercury chloride is

effective in producing coagulation but not in giving rise to the familiar optical effect, usually regarded as characteristic of coagulation. Further work in this line has shown that the above results in viscosity and transparency measurements are but two of the evidences—which are being accumulated in these laboratories—of the anomalies in the behaviour of mercury salts when used as coagulants. These results will be published shortly. From analogy with the results of viscosity mentioned above, it is suggested that transparency also at any rate in the case of colloids, might be more a macroscopic and body property, than a singular function of such micellar constants like charge, size and so forth, variable during coagulation.

The view has been emphasised in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*) that contrary to the simple mechanism postulated in Smoluchowski's theory, coagulation might consist of a series of micellar and allied changes, and that a given property selected for measuring coagulation might not be sensitive to some of these changes. The present results of the non-variation of viscosity, transparency and opacity, measured separately during coagulations with mercury chloride, give experimental support to the above view. Further work is now needed to elucidate in general the principal determinants of the above quantities, *viz.*, viscosity, transparency (and opacity) in coagulating sols. If, however, during a given stage of coagulation, the constituent changes taking place are such as not to influence the property selected for measuring coagulation, then the corresponding section of the coagulation-time curve will have a reduced gradient characteristic of the so-called S-shape, and give but spurious evidence of *autocatalysis* (*cf.* curve 4, Fig. 5). This possibility is of some considerable significance since not a few workers have tried to show that *autocatalysis* might be a *general* description of the coagulation phenomena.

SUMMARY.

1. Measurements have been made of the viscosity, transparency and of the opacity of colloid arsenious sulphide sols of varying colloid contents in the presence of mercury chloride. It has been found that the above quantities do not show an over-all change as a result of coagulation, with the above coagulant.

2. Normal variations in the above properties were observed when cadmium and potassium chlorides were used under the same conditions, and also when but small quantities of them were added to mercury chloride used as a coagulant.

3. Further evidence is obtained to support the view suggested earlier that coagulation is not time-continuous but 'zonal,' and that this feature becomes more pronounced the *slower* the change.

4. It is suggested that both the viscosity and transparency (and therefore opacity) in colloids are functions partly of micellar constants such as the charge, size and specially the shape, etc., and of certain bulk or macroscopic properties of the system as a whole and that the latter might be the more potent factor.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BENARES.

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Studies in the Anthraquinone Series. Attempts to synthesise Anthraquinone Carboxylic Acids of the Morindone Type.

BY P. C. MITTER AND (MISS) TANIMA SEN-GUPTA.

Among the naturally occurring anthraquinone derivatives, carboxylic acids are known only in the madder and emodin groups. The acids occurring in madder are munjisthin and pseudo-purpurin while those belonging to the emodin group are rhein and emodic acid. It appeared to us to be of interest to synthesise acids of the morindone type, which might occur in natural products.

An anthraquinone derivative of the morindone type containing a carboxyl group and not less than two hydroxyl groups may have one or other of four alternative formulae A to D.

